

New Synthetic Analogues of Angiotensin II

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Two new synthetic analogues of 5-Isoleucine angiotensin II, and 5-valine angiotensin II containing fluoroproline in position 7, has been synthesized.

THE chemical structure of the hormones formed by enzymatic action on serum proteins "angiotensin II" are completely established^{1,2}, and they have been synthesized.³⁻⁷

Structure activity relationship of synthetic variation of angiotensin II has held an important place in pharmaceutical chemistry, pharmacology, and biochemistry⁸⁻¹⁰.

For this purpose two new synthetic analogues of 5-Isoleucine angiotensin II, and 5-Valine angiotensin II containing fluoroproline in position 7 has been synthesized. Fluoroproline was used because of the unusual and often unexpected properties which the fluorine atom gives to the molecule, also some fluorinated aminoacids possess outstanding effectiveness as competitive inhibitors^{1,9}.

Z-Pro(4F) ONP¹³ was condensed with L-phenylalanine to give Z-Pro(4F)-L-phe-OH(I). The benzyloxycarbonyl group of the protected dipeptide was eliminated by using hydrogen bromide in acetic acid¹⁴ without any effect on the fluorine atom. The tri II, tetra (III_a, III_b), Penta (IV_a, IV_b), hexa (V_a, V_b), hepta (VI_a, VI_b), and octa (VII_a, VII_b) peptides was prepared stepwise using the *p*-nitrophenyl ester method by the following scheme.

The structures of octa peptides (VII_a, VII_b) was confirmed by its analytical data, and by amino acid analysis after its hydrolysis with 6 N HCl at 110° for about 24 hr. The protected groups used for the protection of the octa peptides was eliminated by catalytic hydrogenation (H₂/Pd)¹⁵, and some biological testings are under consideration.

Experimental

The time allowed for the completion of the reaction and the purity of the prepared compounds was controlled by means of thin-layer chromatography (T. L. C) using freshly prepared solvent (butanol-water-acetic acid 62 : 26 : 12). T. L. C. plates were prepared by slurring kiesel gel on microscopic slides (0.25 mm thick) and dried at 120° for 1/2 hr. Detection of the spots were achieved by putting the plates in a closed tank containing iodine. N-benzyloxycarbonylamino acids and peptides were detected by ninhydrin spray on chromatograms after treating with hydrogen bromide in acetic acid at room temperature (20°) for 1 hr. Melting points were determined on Callen-Kamp melting point apparatus and were uncorrected.

Preparation of Z-L-Pro(4f)-L-phe-OH (I). To a solution of Z-L-Pro(4f) ONP (1.12g) in ethylacetate

(10 ml); L-phe-OH (1.65g) in ethylacetate (10-ml) was added, and the reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. After the time allowed was consumed, the precipitate was filtered, washed with 2N HCl, 5% NaHCO₃, ether, and recrystallized from ethylacetate to give Z-L-Pro (4f)-L-phe-OH (2.5 g, 80%), m. p. 140°-42°, R_t 0.43, * $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -41^\circ$ (C=1, in D. M. F.), Found, C, 66.39; H, 5.47; N, 6.91; F, 4.71; C₂₂H₂₂N₂O₄F; required, C, 66.50; H, 5.54; N, 7.05; F, 4.78%.

Preparation of Z-L-His-L-Pro(4f)-L-phe-OH(II).

To Z-L-Pro (4f)-L-phe OH (0.8 g) in acetic acid (2.25 ml), was added hydrogen bromide in acetic acid (2N; 1.8 ml). After 1 hr at room temperature dry ether was added. The precipitated hydrobromide was dissolved in the minimum volume of D. M. F.; triethylamine (2.6 ml) was added followed by Z-L-His-ONP¹⁶ (0.6 g). After 18 hours at room temperature the solid mass was mixed with ethylacetate (75 ml), filtered, washed with 2NHCl, 5% NaHCO₃, ether, and recrystallized from ethylacetate to give Z-L-His-L-pro(4f)-L-phe-OH as colourless needle (1.3 g, 83%), m.p. 146-48°, R_t 0.45; $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -49^\circ$ (in D. M. F.), (Found, C, 62.82; H, 5.37; N, 13.02; F, 3.49; C₂₈H₂₈N₅O₅F; required, C, 62.95; H, 5.43; N, 13.10; F, 3.55%.

Preparation of Z-L-Ileu-L-His-L Pro(4f)-L-phe OH IIIa. To Z-L-His-L-Pro (4f)-L-Phe-OH (0.7 g) in acetic acid (2.25 ml); was added hydrogen bromide in acetic acid (2N, 1.8 ml). After 1 hr at room temperature dry ether was added. The precipitated hydrobromide was filtered, washed with ether, and dried over NaOH. The solid mass was dissolved in the minimum amount of D. M. F., triethylamine (2.6 ml) was added followed by Z-L-Ileu-ONP¹⁶(0.5 g). After 18 hr. at room temperature the solid mass was mixed with ethylacetate (75 ml), filtered, washed with 2N HCl, 5% NaHCO₃, ether, and recrystallized from ethylacetate to give Z-L-Ileu-L-His-L-Pro(4f)-L-phe-OH as colourless needle (1.25 g, 85%), m. p. 150°-51°, R_t 0.49, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -53^\circ$ (C=1, in D. M. F.), Found C, 62.97; H, 6.03; N, 12.87; F, 2.84; C₃₄H₄₀N₆O₅F, required C, 63.06; H, 6.18; N, 12.98; F, 2.93%.

Preparation of Z-L-Val-L-His-L-Pro(4f)-L-phe-OH IIIb. The above experiment was repeated but with Z-L-Val-ONP (0.45 g). At the end of the experiment the precipitate was filtered, washed with 2NHCl, 5% NaHCO₃, ether, and recrystallized from ethylacetate to give Z-L-Val-L-His-L-Pro(4f)-L-phe-OH as colourless needle (1.2 g, 85%), m. p. 138-39°, R_t 0.51 $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -47^\circ$ | C=1, in D. M. F. |, (Found C, 62.41; H, 5.92; N, 13.14; F, 2.91; C₂₈H₂₈N₅O₅F; required C, 62.55; H, 6.00 N; 13.27; F, 3.00%.

Preparation of Z-L-Tyr-L-Ileu-L-His-L-Pro(4f)-L-Phe-OH IV_a. To a solution of Z-L-Ileu-L-His-L-Pro(4f)-L-Phe-OH(0.72 g) in acetic acid (2.25 ml) was added hydrogen bromide in acetic acid (2N, 1.8 ml), After one hour at room temperature dry ether was added. The precipitated hydrobromide was filtered, washed with ether, and dried over NaOH. The solid mass was dissolved in the minimum amount of D. M. F., triethyla-

mine (2.6 ml) was added followed by Z-L-Tyr-ONP¹⁶ (0.6 g). After 18 hr. at room temperature, the solid mass was mixed with ethylacetate (75 ml), filtered, washed with 2N HCl, 5% NaHCO₃, ether, and recrystallized from ethylacetate to give Z-L-Tyr-Ileu-L-His-L-Pro (4f)-L-Phe-OH as colourless needle (1.3 g, 85%), m. p. 167°-69°; R_t 0.55; $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -63^\circ$ (C=1, in D. M. F.), (Found C, 63.58; H, 5.92; N, 13.71 F, 2.26; C₄₈H₄₈N₇O₈ F, required C, 63.70 H, 6.04; N, 13.82; F, 2.34%.

Preparation of Z-L-Tyr-L-Val-L-His-L-Pro (4f)-L-Phe-OH. IV_b. The above experiment was repeated but with Z-L-Val-L-His-L-Pro(4f)-L-Phe-OH (0.65 g). At the end of the experiment the precipitate was filtered, washed with 2N HCl, 5% NaHCO₃, ether and recrystallized from ethylacetate to give Z-L-Tyr-L-Val-L-Pro (4f)-L-Phe-OH as colourless needle (1.25 g, 86%), m. p. 162°-64°; R_t 0.56; $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -55^\circ$ (C=1, in D. M. F.), (Found C, 63.22; H, 5.68; N, 12.19, F, 2.25, C₄₇H₄₇N₇O₈F, required C, 63.31 H, 5.77; N, 12.31; F, 2.38%.

Preparation of Z-L-Val-Tyr-L-Ileu-L-His-L-Pro (4f)-L-Phe-OH V_a. To Z-L-Try-L-Ileu-L-His-L-Pro(4f)-L-Phe-OH (0.8 g) in acetic acid (2.5 ml) was added hydrogen bromide in acetic acid (2N, 1.8 ml). After 1 hr. at room temperature dry ether was added. The precipitated hydrobromide was filtered, washed with ether and dried over NaOH. The solid mass was dissolved in the minimum amount of D. M. F., triethylamine (2.6 ml) was added followed by Z-L-Val-ONP(0.45 g). After 18 hr. at room temperature the solid mass was mixed with ethylacetate (75 ml), filtered, washed with 2N HCl, 5% NaHCO₃, ether, and recrystallized from ethylacetate to give Z-L-Val-L-Tyr-L-Ileu-L-His-L-Pro(4f)-L-Phe-OH as colourless needle (1.26 g); 83%), m. p. 178-80; R_t 0.6; $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -69^\circ$ (C=1, in D. M. F.), (Found C, 63.24; H, 6.29; N, 12.21; F, 2.20; C₄₈H₅₈N₈O₉F, required C, 63.36; H, 6.38; N, 12.32; F, 2.08).

Preparation of Z-L-Val-L-Tyr-L-Val-L-His-L-Pro (4f)-L-Phe-OH V_b. The above experiment was repeated but with Z-L-Tyr-L-Val-L-His-L-Pro(4f)-L-Phe-OH (0.75 g). At the end of the experiment the precipitate was filtered, washed with 2N HCl, 5% NaHCO₃, ether, and recrystallized from ethylacetate to give Z-L-Val-L-Tyr-L-Val-L-His-L-Pro(4f)-L-Phe-OH as colourless needle (1.2 g; 85%) m. p. 173°-75°; R_t 0.62; $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -63$ (C=1, in D. M. F.), (Found C, 62.93; H, 6.14; N, 12.39; F, 2.06; C₄₇H₅₈N₈O₉F; required, C, 63.01, H, 6.25; N; 12.51 F, 2.21%.

Preparation of Z-L-Arg (NO₂)-L-Val-L-Tyr-L-Ileu-L-His-L-Pro(4f)-L-Phe-OH VI_a. To Z-L-Val-L-Tyr-L-Ileu-L-His-L-Pro(4f)-L-Phe-OH (0.9 g) in acetic acid (2.5 ml) was added hydrogen bromide in acetic acid (2N, 1.8 ml). After 1 hr. at room temperature dry ether was added. The precipitated hydrobromide was filtered, washed with ether, and dried over NaOH. The solid mass was dissolved in the minimum amount of D. M. F., triethylamine (2.6 ml) was added followed by Z-L-Arg (NO₂)-ONP(0.35 g). After 18 hr. at room temperature, the solid mass was mixed with ethylacetate

(75 ml), filtered, washed with 2*N* HCl, 5% NaHCO₃, ether, and recrystallized from ethylacetate to give Z-L-Arg(NO₂)-L-Val-L-Tyr-L-Ileu-L-His-L-Pro (4F)-L-Phe-OH as colourless needle (1.4g, 83%), m. p. 190-92, R_t 0.67; $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -72^\circ$ (C=1, in D. M. F.), (found C, 58.20; H, 6.12; N, 16.33; F, 1.68; C₅₄H₆₉N₁₃O₁₂F required C, 58.37; H, 6.21; N, 16.40; F, 1.71%).

Preparation of Z-L-Arg(NO₂)-L-Val-L-Tyr-L-Val-L-His-L-Pro(4F)-L-Phe-OH VI_b. The above experiment was repeated but with ZL-Val-L-Tyr-L-Val-L-His-L-Pro, (4F)-L-Phe-OH (0.85 g). At the end of the experiment, the precipitate was filtered, washed with 2*N* HCl, 5% NaHCO₃, ether, and recrystallized from ethyl acetate to give Z-L-Arg(NO₂)-L-Val-L-Tyr-L-Val-L-His-L-Pro(4F)-L-Phe-OH as colourless needle (1.3 g, 85%), m. p. 180-82; R_t 0.7 $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -68^\circ$ (C=1, in D.M.F.), (found C, 57.93; H, 6.02; N, 16.53; F, 1.66; C₅₃H₆₇N₁₃O₁₂F; required C, 58.02; H, 6.11; N, 16.60; F, 1.73%).

Preparation of Z-L-Asp-L-Arg(NO₂)-L-Val-L-Tyr-L-Ileu-L-His-L-Pro(4f)-L-Phe-OH VII_a. To Z-L-Arg(NO₂)-L-Val-L-Tyr-L-Ileu-L-Pro(4f)-L-Phe-OH (0.9 g) in acetic acid (3 ml) was added hydrogen bromide in acetic acid (2*N*, 1.8 ml). After one hour at room temperature, dry ether was added. The precipitated hydrobromide was filtered, washed with ether and dried over NaOH. The solid mass was dissolved in the minimum amount of D. M. F. triethylamine (2.6 ml) was added followed by Z-L-Asp-ONP (0.35 g). After 18 hour at room temperature, the solid mass was mixed with ethylacetate (75 ml), filtered, washed with 2*N* HCl, 5% NaHCO₃, ether, and recrystallized from ethylacetate to give Z-L-Asp-L-Arg(NO₂)-L-Val-L-Tyr-L-Ileu-L-His-L-Pro(4f)-L-Phe-OH as colourless needle (1.4 g, 87%), m.p. 205°-7°, R_t 0.73; $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -77^\circ$ (C=1, in D. M. F.), (found C, 56.73; H, 5.92; N, 15.91; F, 1.49 C₅₈H₇₄N₁₄O₁₅F; required C, 56.81; H, 6.04; N, 16.00; F, 1.55%). Amino acid analysis: Asparatic acid 0.99 (1 mol), Arginine 1.02 (1 mol), valine; 1.00 (1 mol), tyrosine 0.97 (1 mol), iso-Leucine 1.00 (1 mol), histidine 0.99 (1 mol), fluoroproline 1.00 (1 mol), and phenylalanine 1.02 (1 mol).

Preparation of Z-L-Asp-L-Arg(NO₂)-L-Val-L-Tyr-L-Val-L-His-L-Pro(4f)-L-Phe-OH VII_b: The above experiment was repeated but with Z-L-Arg(NO₂)-L-Val-L-Tyr-L-Val-L-His-L-Pro(4f)-L-Phe-OH (0.9 g). At the end of the experiment, the precipitate was filtered, washed with 2*N*HCl, 5% NaHCO₃, ether, and recrystallized from ethylacetate to give Z-L-Asp-L-Arg(NO₂)-L-Val-L-Tyr-L-Val-L-His-L-Pro(4f)-L-Phe-OH as colourless needle (1.35 g; 85%), m. p. 197°-99°, R_t 0.75; $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -75^\circ$ (C=1, in D. M. F.), (found C, 56.35; H, 5.00; N, 16.03; F, 1.47; C₅₇H₇₂N₁₄O₁₅F; required C, 56.48; H, 5.11; N, 16.18; F, 1.56%). Amino acid analysis: Aspartic acid 1.00 (1 mol), arginine 1.02 (1 mol), valine 2.00 (2 mol), tyrosine 0.97 (1 mol) histidine 0.99 (1 mol), fluoroproline 1.00 (1 mol), and phenylalanine 1.02 (1 mol).

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